

Volunteer Recruitment Strategy

By the end of the ACTION project, we will need to have recruited at least 200 participants across two different types of activity: data analysis **microtasks** and **LCA research**. These activities are very different and require different—but linked—approaches.

Microtasks

Introduction

Our data analysis microtasks are intended to engage large numbers of participants. As each task should be designed to require as little technical knowledge as possible, participants should require little-to-no training and be able to start contributing almost straight away. Consequently, these microtasks have the potential to engage a large and diverse audience, which should be reflected in our communications.

Who are we trying to reach?

These microtasks are especially likely to appeal to people with an interest in technology, repair, data, environmentalism and/or environmental policy. This describes much of our core audience, particularly within our community and followers on social media. Given the low barrier to participation, we should also aim to reach outside our existing audience where possible, in order to bring in those who may not have encountered citizen science before. We should aim to engage at least 200 microtask participants across all three tasks.

What channels and messages will we use?

The exact message will change depending on the focus of each of the three microtasks we will run. But our overarching messaging should revolve around the following themes:

- Participation can help us understand why our devices break and how they can be made to last longer and be easier to fix
- This work can help influence new eco-rules (primarily in the EU) to make products easier to fix, and by doing so reduce our impact on the planet
- Participation can help counteract/balance out corporate lobbyists by making data from real communities on the ground more accessible
- Participation is quick, easy and fun!
- It's possible to make a difference even while in-person repair events aren't possible

For all messages, the CTA should be to visit the more recent microtask page on our community platform.

We can use the following channels:

Social media

Twitter

Our largest following is on Twitter, where interactions tend to be fast-paced, dynamic and direct. Our tone tends to be more activist-like and unapologetically geeky than on other

channels. Here, we can promote the more technical and political angles to the microtask activities

Instagram

Instagram is a newer platform for us. Given its visual focus, this is a good place to share infographics and other imagery to demonstrate the potential impacts of each microtask (e.g. a diagram of a smartphone indicating the most common points of failure, with a CTA for helping us drill down further through a microtask).

Facebook

Facebook is our most community-facing social media platform. Messaging here should emphasise the community-driven nature of the data collected and analysis. Frustratingly, the algorithm prioritises divisive content, so we should perhaps consider trialing 'community versus big tech' messaging.

Our community platform (inc. forum)

Our community platform is home to our most engaged community members and contains an active forum. Here, we can assume a certain degree of pre-existing knowledge and be a little more technical with our messaging. With that said, we also need to bear in mind that all communications should be as accessible as possible to the broadest range of people.

We should create a dedicated forum topic for each microtask in the Repair Data category, potentially pinning each one until the next becomes available to increase visibility. Each topic should introduce the current microtask, offering an explanation of how it works, why we're running it, the benefits of participation and instructions for how to get involved. These will also be interactive channels for discussion, allowing for engagement with the tasks outside of the tasks themselves.

Our mailing list(s)

Our monthly newsletter and especially our dedicated data mailing list are potentially great ways to reach more participants. Messages here should be similar in nature to our community platform, but, for the general mailing list, tailored around a specific talking point to contextualise the activity (e.g. upcoming Ecodesign consultation or another political development).

Timings

We should ideally push out co-ordinated messages across all platforms as each microtask launches. During the course of the microtask, we should post updates on social media and the community platform and be sure to report the results afterwards (thanking participants on our community platform in particular). Give we are planning three microtasks, we should be cautious about over-saturating each channel with repeated/similar CTAs to avoid alienating or annoying our audience.

LCA Research

Introduction

The work to update our LCA reference data is very different to our microtasks. We're aiming to engage 6 volunteers to work on an in-depth research project over the course of three months.

Who are we trying to reach?

A small number of highly-motivated volunteers - ideally people with a strong interest in environmental issues and keen to learn more about upstream industrial processes. To ensure a wholistic approach in this work, we should aim to engage participants from a range of backgrounds (e.g. academia, community organising, technical repair, data science and so on).

What channels and messages will we use?

The main message should focus on the following points:

- For many of the devices we buy, most of the negative environmental impacts have already happened before we turn them on.
- But these impacts are hidden and mysterious. We want to pull back the curtain and see what's really going on (in order to then help others understand them better too)
- This will also help us build a stronger case for repair (using the materials and devices we've already manufactured for longer can reduce these upstream impacts)
- This work will help communities around the world better understand and communicate their impacts as well as make the case for repair locally
- By getting involved, you can learn about these impacts and how they are calculated

We don't need huge numbers of participants for this work, so can afford to be more targeted with recruitment messages. We could also use this work as a 'take the next step' opportunity for people who engage with a microtask, building a funnel of increased engagement with a view to welcoming them into the community.

Timings

We should consider a co-ordinated push on social media, the community platform and email channels to engage an initial cohort of participants. After this, recruitment messages could be combined with 'project update' messaging (e.g. 'we've discovered that making a laptop produces x kg of CO2 before it's even switched on. Help us learn more...')